

SITE GPR	YEAR 11	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.350 Max: 62.564	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1408 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #2054-56		Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
DEFINITION fill above tiles (SU 1466)				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1384, 1279	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1483	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Composition <input type="checkbox"/> Compaction			FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition			
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay 10% silt 85% sand 5% <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive	
Anthropic		Geological		Organic		Compaction <input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)		Color <input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)						
Northern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original		
Southern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		grave 45		
Western Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
Eastern Limit		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit				
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE						
Is equal to:				Is bound to (only for masonry):		
Is abutted by:				Abuts:		
Is covered by: 1284, 1279 (but was prob. cut through)				Covers: 1466		
Is cut by:				Cuts:		
Is filled by:				Fills: 1483		
OBSERVATIONS excavated after rain storm with trowels						
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: located fairly central within Area B, a bit north of center located within drainage channel Shape: ovular						
For layers complete this section: Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): layer is in two levels, to the west the layer is apx 15cm high while to the east the tiles are already visible (at a lower slope). Both slopes are relatively even Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): rocky inclusions in the fill Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): thicker in west Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commigled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify) bedrock						
For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:				Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North): 		

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)
 Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

fill of cut 1483, soil placed above tiles (most likely a burial) after deposition. Later above this level on the west the sewer embankment was placed (601384). This later sewer explains why the fill to the east is less thick than to the west, in the east the fill was cut down into to make the drainage channel. Actually it is to assume that the grave, which fill is described here, was dug after the abandonment of the sewer.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

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